

Deliverable 9.1 – Communication Plan

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Declaration: Any work or result described therein is a genuine output of the AtlantECO project. Any other source will be properly referenced where and when relevant.

Table of Content

1	Version History	3
2	Executive summary	4
3	Introduction	5
4	Vision and objectives in a global context	6
4.1	Bringing the Ocean Microbiome to the heart of the United Nations Decade of Ocean Sciences	7
4.2	Contribution to the EU policy agenda	7
5	Communication strategy	8
5.1	System analysis	8
5.2	Linking communication objectives to stakeholders and messages	8
6	Communication campaigns	15
6.1	Campaigns for engagement and participation	15
6.2	Campaigns for action and legacy	19
7	Communication resources	21
7.1	Branding	21
7.2	Developing communication content	23
7.3	Delivering communication: resources, material and events.	24
8	Monitoring and measuring impact	30
8.1	Monitoring and reporting communication activities in the project	30
8.2	Key Performance Indicators	30

Pending approval

1 Version History

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2 Executive summary

The Deliverable “Communication Plan” is produced as part of the Work Package 9 “Communication, capacity building and outreach” and sets out to establish the initial strategy for communication to support the activities and objectives of the project and contribute to sustainable widespread impact.

It is established as a living document which will evolve as the project develops to ensure that communication activities remain relevant to the progress of the project, its achievements and the context within which it operates. In this initial version we present:

- the vision of the AtlantECO project in the current context
- the communication system targeted:
 - communication aims
 - the stakeholders
 - the key messages
- the strategy to deliver and measure impact
 - the planned campaigns and activities
 - the communication resources
 - the approach to monitor and measure performance of communication activities

Within the current sanitary crisis context due to Covid-19, contingency measures will be implemented where and when the planned events described here are not possible to implement. Digital platforms and streaming systems will allow remote attendance when in person events are not possible.

Furthermore, in person events will always be organised in line with the restrictions and regulations in place at the time of the event

This document is based on the terms and conditions established in the Grant Agreement (GA) and its Annexes, as well as in the Consortium Agreement (CA).

Pending approval

3 Introduction

The ambition of AtlantECO is to develop and apply a novel, unifying framework that provides knowledge-based resources to design policies, support decision making and engage with citizens to encourage responsible behaviour to manage the Atlantic system and protect its Ecosystem Services provision.

The aim of AtlantECO is to determine the structure and function of Atlantic microbiome in the context of ocean circulation and presence of pollutants, e.g., plastics, to assess its role in driving the dynamics of Atlantic ecosystems at basin and regional scales; its potential of being used as a sensor of ecosystem state and the mechanisms by which it drives the provision of five ES. This is key to improve our predictions on future provision of ES in the basin and to favour the establishment of a sustainable Blue Growth strategy for an All-Atlantic community.

To realise this vision, AtlantECO has four objectives which are to

- 1) Assess dynamics of Atlantic marine ecosystems, their ES provision and the interplay of both with socio-economic activities.
- 2) Increase knowledge and data on microbiomes, plastics, the plastisphere and carbon fluxes that support ecosystems at basin scale using best practices and integrative sampling strategies, novel genomics, imaging and biogeochemical methods, bioinformatics and modelling approaches.
- 3) Assess and predict the cumulative impacts of multiple stressors on ecosystem status and dynamics and ES provision, identifying their drivers and role on tipping points, assessing their changes in recovery of ecosystem structures, functions and services, and developing eco-socio-economic models to predict future trajectories.
- 4) Deploy a systemic strategy to build capacity and transfer knowledge for a seamless engagement between science, industry, policy, and society. To achieve these objectives AtlantECO brings together experts and pioneers from Europe, South America and South Africa with the relevant resources, knowledge and experience.

The conference “A New Era of Blue Enlightenment”, held in Lisbon in July 2017, presented an ambitious vision for a future integrated Atlantic scientific cooperation program, shared by the European Union, Brazil and South Africa. This vision was expressed in the Belem Statement, a High-Level political declaration signed by the European commissioner for research and innovation, the president of Portugal and ministers from Brazil and South Africa. The *All-Atlantic* projects are now working to deliver the objectives of the Belem Statement.

Within this framework, AtlantECO will highlight the importance of Atlantic marine ecosystems, building synergies with the “sister projects”, we will focus our communication on the microbiome, invisible multitude that drifts in the ocean, as well as on the microplastics and the microbiome which lives on them, and the concept of connectivity or how everything moves around in the ocean.

The AtlantECO communication plan presented in this document identifies the different targets and audiences to be reached for the aims that have been defined. It is created to support the other activities of the project and to facilitate the achievement of the Dissemination and Exploitation Plan. This holistic and systemic approach will help ensure that the expected impacts of AtlantECO are achieved. The plan presented here defines the communication aims, the targeted audiences; the key messages and the plan for delivering the messages through communication campaigns, supported by dedicated resources and activities.

4 Vision and objectives in a global context

The ocean and its ecosystems are key to life on Earth. Over the course of billions of years, they have fine-tuned the planet to make it hospitable to the vast diversity of life we see today. However, only during the last few decades, we have begun to unravel in detail the ocean processes that we are still utterly dependent on. There are distressing reports of plummeting fish stocks, charismatic species pushed to the brink of extinction, and the ghostly remains of coral cities. Yet the multitudes of microbes in every drop of seawater have received far less attention, despite their essential roles in nourishing ecosystems, and therefore humans, producing oxygen, and transporting carbon to the deep ocean. And this regardless of the fact that they are, as other species, highly sensitive to temperature change, ocean acidification, and pollution.

Depending on where you cast down your bucket, a typical litre of seawater is home to billions of microbes, mostly made of no more than a single cell. They include prokaryotes such as bacteria and archaea - the most ancient and widespread lifeforms on Earth - breathtakingly diverse marine viruses and eukaryotes such as single-celled phytoplankton, which include delicate prasinophytes, glass-shelled diatoms, spindly dinoflagellates, and chalk-plated coccolithophores. Phytoplankton feed a sensational array of tiny animals known as zooplankton, the base of a food web that nourishes giants such as whales, sharks, manta rays, oarfish, and octopuses. This will be an exciting adventure, one where scientists, sailors, policymakers, entrepreneurs, teachers, and the general public all have a vital role to play, as we embark on the next great exploration of the seas: the ocean microbiome.

But despite their tiny size, microbes are also at risk: climate change and plastic pollution are two different but cumulative impacts that have already been observed as backed by scientific evidence. Building a story with plastics and planktonic organisms can help to link this invisible majority to human activities, behaviours and consumption, with a focus on alternatives for a sustainable and circular blue economy.

Microbes are diverse communities of unicellular organisms and the most common creatures on the planet. Microbes are considered by many only to be bacteria and archaea, but in fact there is also a myriad of single-celled eukaryotes as well, with cells that can be even more complex than the cells that make up the human body. These are sometimes referred to as protists or micro-eukaryotes and include phytoplankton (also known as micro-algae), as well as a range of other single-celled organisms that may eat or live in symbiosis with bacteria or other protists or may themselves be parasites or pathogens or symbionts. Microeukaryotes are not common in the human microbiome, but notable examples include yeasts and other fungi and parasites responsible for malaria, sleeping sickness, and other debilitating diseases. Today we also accept that viruses are part of a microbiome, even though viruses are dependent on other life to replicate. While we typically think of viruses that cause disease in humans, plants and animals, they can also make microbes sick, but they can also give them new capabilities, like antibiotic resistance.

Together, this collection of organisms that make up a microbiome is also called the microbiota. Increasingly evident as the nascent field of 'microbiome science' matures, is that understanding the microbiome not only encompasses identifying the microbiota – i.e., who is present –, but also understanding their "theatre of activity," – i.e., where do they live, what can they do, and what do they do. Measurements and analyses of structural elements, metabolites, and signalling molecules, and the surrounding environmental conditions are grand challenges for humankind. For the human microbiome, the theatre of activity is us, our skin, our gut, or our mouth. For the ocean microbiome, it is the ocean in its full complexity: marine water, sediments, aerosols, fragments of plastics, and all larger organisms, from zooplankton to sharks, penguins, and whales. The ocean microbiome is therefore equivalent to single-celled plankton together with viruses. Multicellular plankton such as copepods and jellyfish are not part of the ocean microbiome. But they are intricately linked to it because of their often-direct interactions with single-celled plankton.

4.1 Bringing the Ocean Microbiome to the heart of the United Nations Decade of Ocean Sciences

For the next ten years, the United Nations has declared a Decade of Ocean Sciences for Sustainable Development (2021-2030), a unique opportunity to fill gaps in our knowledge about the ocean microbiome. In that sense, AtlantECO will be committed in the next five years to promote the importance of the Microbiome and to communicate in this niche within the framework of the All-Atlantic sister projects, adding content, stories, images and evidence that raise awareness around the rich, but fragile, Atlantic ecosystem. AtlantECO contributes to all UN Ocean Decade objectives, and to many of its challenges and desired outcomes. Indeed, it will carry out research on many oceanographic topics and contribute to a better understanding of the microbiome, as well as building knowledge on plastic and chemical pollutants in the South Atlantic and in the rivers of the region. This research will foster the capacity of ocean science to deliver high quality ocean data that can inform changes in society. It will contribute to the need for an accessible Ocean with FAIR access to data, delivering the biggest data collection to date for the South Atlantic and making it available through open data platforms. In addition, the ocean literacy and advocacy activities carried out will contribute to a better understanding of the importance of the microbiome and the value of making science-based policies for policy makers and industries. The capacity building programme will increase the resources available for ocean science and sustainable development in countries bordering the South Atlantic.

This is a crucial time for the world's oceans, and knowledge acquired from studying the populations, environments and dynamics of the ocean microbiome will be fundamental in informing new or improved global governance regulations and policies expected in the coming years.

4.2 Contribution to the EU policy agenda

In 2016, the European Commission and the European External Action Service launched an important milestone document: The International Ocean Governance agenda. Adopted at the highest political level, the agenda focused on the main political processes being discussed in many forums at regional and global levels. The objective was to structure the EU contribution towards healthy, clean, secure, safe and sustainably managed oceans. The agenda held a consultation period, and identified 50 actions to improve the international framework, reduce threats, promote a sustainable blue economy, and strengthen international ocean research and data.

During the recent consultation for the European Green Deal, the High Representative/Vice President Josep Borrell said: *"The protection of our oceans is a global challenge that requires a collective response. The European Union is doing its part and ready to do more. We are determined to continue to fulfil our responsibility towards our citizens and to work with partners across the world. We all want sustainable and healthy oceans and to improve their governance."*

In addition, the importance of the marine and maritime activities has prompted the creation of the EU Integrated Maritime Policy (IMP), and related directives and strategies (EU Blue Growth Strategy BGS, EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive MSFD, EU Maritime Spatial Planning MSP, Integrated Coastal Zone Management ICZM).

AtlantECO will contribute to these efforts by building a specific set of actions for the Atlantic Ocean and by participating in International forums and High-Level Conferences such as the UN Ocean Conference, the revision process on the Sustainable development agenda or the discussions on the Biodiversity Beyond National jurisdiction.

5 Communication strategy

5.1 System analysis

In order to develop an efficient and effective communication plan a system analysis was performed. The system includes all stakeholders who need to be involved for AtlantECO to deliver impact which is relevant and sustainable within its specific remit of interest. During the analysis, the communication objectives have been defined and, for each, targeted stakeholders, key messages, means of delivery and links to specific communication campaigns have been established. The overview of the system aims is presented in Figure 1, then the following sections will provide the details for each.

Figure 1 AtlantECO: communication plan, system analysis overview.

5.2 Linking communication objectives to stakeholders and messages

The communication plan will focus on the specific topics and activities of the AtlantECO project to ensure that there is a better understanding of the phenomena (microbiome, plastics and plastisphere, and connectivity)

studied by a wide array of stakeholders, from experts to the general public. It is therefore essential to adapt the messages to the audiences targeted and contextualise these scientific concepts within relatable issues for each target audience. Below we provide details of the objective identified through the system analysis in terms of target audiences (stakeholders) and the key messages that will be delivered to them. In the subsequent sections we will describe the activities and resources to be deployed in order to deliver the communication plan.

In this communication plan, stakeholder groups are mentioned but the specific stakeholders targeted are not listed, instead AtlantECO has developed and will maintain its stakeholder database as a dynamic document outside of the communication objectives.

5.2.1 Ensuring project visibility

The aim is to ensure that as many people as possible are aware of the AtlantECO project and understand why it exists, what it does and what impacts it has.

5.2.1.1 Stakeholders

This objective covers the widest array of stakeholders as delivering project visibility will ensure that all other communication objectives are also supported. It is important that all target audiences are aware of the project, its objectives, focus and progress so that they can understand how and when to engage in more specific activities that are relevant to their stake.

5.2.1.2 Key communication messages

Since all stakeholders are targeted in this objective, the content and messages will be the most general and accessible of the communication plan. This means that messages will cover the basic information about the project in a manner that is understandable by most audiences. This objective will focus on providing information on:

- **AtlantECO scientific pillars:** microbiomes are crucial for life on Earth, including for regulating the plastic fate. We have developed a unified framework to understand, assess and predict its status and functioning.
 - Ocean microbiome: The ocean microbiome is an invisible but essential part of life. It supports life in the oceans and its services to society, is one of the lungs of the climate system. Climate

- change and pollution effects on the ocean microbiomes are already visible. New tools allow to assess the ecosystem health.
- Plastics and the plastisphere: Most of plastics in the oceans and sediments are made of microscopic fragments that are omnipresent. They enter into the food web via the plankton and their fate and toxicity are influenced by the microbes living on them. We have to map both the plastics and its microbiome.
 - Seascape and connectivity: There is one single connected ocean. Ocean currents transport plankton and pollutants across the entire Atlantic, connecting highly polluted regions with cleaner ones as well as connecting highly productive regions with oceanic deserts. To understand and predict the ecosystem functioning and its services we have to understand the role of oceanic currents.
 - **AtlantECO activities**
 - Major milestones: highlighting the main events of the project such as updates from flagship sampling cruises, attendance at and contributions to high-level policy events
 - Opportunities for the public: e.g., port call events, museum exhibitions.
 - **AtlantECO achievements**
 - Results in a nutshell: explaining what the outcomes of the project mean for society, for the ocean, for blue growth and all the sectors that can benefit from the innovations and advances delivered.

5.2.2 Raising awareness

The aim is to increase awareness and understanding of the ocean and what influence it has on different aspects of society, as well as the influence society has on it.

5.2.2.1 Stakeholders

Ocean literacy communication campaigns will focus on:

- the younger population, through direct engagement and through a programme of capacity building with education networks including teachers and school associations through UNESCO-IOC.
- local populations with project events, including the public, decision makers and professionals.
- society at large through the media channels of the project

5.2.2.2 Key communication messages

Ocean literacy, as presented by UNESCO/IOC, is defined as the understanding of our influence on the ocean, and the ocean's influence on us – including as a major regulator of the Earth's climate. As such, ocean literacy is an essential tool for all citizens, whether we live along the coastline, up on the mountains or in a landlocked country.

Communication messages will be based on existing resources, the project Ocean Literacy programme and other material developed for the project, and will focus on the Atlantic Ocean, and the three scientific pillars of AtlantECO (Microbiome, plastics & the plastisphere, seascape & connectivity). The messages will be co-developed with indigenous populations to ensure relevance of the programme, local ownership of the initiatives and sustainability of the process.

5.2.3 Promoting scientific participation and citizen science

The aim is to make stakeholders aware of the opportunity to participate in sampling activities of the AtlantECO project.

5.2.3.1 Stakeholders

This will be aimed at citizens, sailors and scientists who are interested and able to contribute to the sampling efforts of AtlantECO.

5.2.3.2 Key communication messages

The communication campaign will focus on informing stakeholders about the opportunity to get involved in citizen science activities (e.g., Sail-4-science, Ocean Sampling Day) and provide all the required details for them to know how and when to get involved.

5.2.4 Supporting capacity building programme

The aim is to inform stakeholders about the opportunity for training events, and to provide access to training resources, both existing and developed through the project.

5.2.4.1 Stakeholders

Capacity building will reach the following audiences:

- Early Career Researchers: for theoretical and practical training in the field and disciplines of marine science, and complementary skills
- Researchers and Professionals: for hands-on training and participation in project activities
- Teachers: for co-developing and implementing the Ocean Literacy programme.

5.2.4.2 Key communication messages

The key messages will focus on promotion of events organised and delivered through AtlantECO or the wider community of projects as supported by the AANCHOR project. Information will be provided on what the training is about, who it is relevant for, where and when it will take place and where applicable how to get support from the project to participate in the event.

5.2.5 Supporting the engagement with decision makers

The aim is to engage with targeted stakeholders to support existing and new initiatives for sustainable management of ocean resources, specifically concentrating on the foci of AtlantECO.

5.2.5.1 Stakeholders

Stakeholders include all individuals and organisations who are involved in discussing, deciding, implementing and supporting the healthy sustainable management of Ocean resources. This includes but is not limited to policy makers, management authorities, funding agencies, marine/environment monitoring bodies and institutes, ecosystem services providers, etc. The full list of stakeholders will be defined for the specific issues to be discussed during the project implementation and be kept up to date in the stakeholder database.

5.2.5.2 Key communication messages

The communication messages will highlight the importance of advances made in the project, specifically around the three scientific pillars of AtlantECO and inform stakeholders on their relevance for sustainable management of marine resources.

Communication campaigns will focus on the five project case studies and their specific areas of application (geographical and sectoral) as defined in the description of action. Relevant stakeholders will be targeted to ensure they participate in the discussions so that recommendations made are co-developed.

5.2.6 Supporting optimal use of innovation potential

The aim is to promote the achievements of the project and explain how the results will lead to the development of new products and services as defined in the Dissemination and Exploitation Plan of AtlantECO.

5.2.6.1 Stakeholders

The stakeholders are all individuals and organisations who will be using the results emerging from the project to propose innovative offers onto the Blue Economy market and its linked services. The specific stakeholders will be identified as part of the exploitation planning activities and feed into the stakeholder database and will build onto the initial group of early adopters who are already collaborating with the project partners in case studies.

5.2.6.2 Key communication messages

Messages will focus on explaining how social, environmental and economic benefits will be achieved through research-based innovation and new products and services in marine technology and biotechnology.

5.2.7 Supporting access to results and data

The aim is to promote the availability of the project results and share the scientific advances achieved, supporting of the Dissemination and Exploitation Plan of AtlantECO.

5.2.7.1 Stakeholders

Stakeholders are all individuals or organisations that are interested in accessing and/or using the results and data from the AtlantECO project. Primarily this will include the scientific community, i.e., research and academia and the organisations that will access and use the data for marine monitoring and management.

5.2.7.2 Key communication messages

Communication messages will help promote the dissemination events such as conferences attended and/or organised, the webinars and other online dissemination occurrences, summer schools and training opportunities and encourage participation of stakeholders in such events. In addition, links to access publications, recordings of events and data base resources will be provided on all communication channels.

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6 Communication campaigns

The communication plan revolves around a set of campaigns to support the objectives identified earlier. The campaigns are designed to follow the progress of the project from inset to closure to deliver the right message at the right time to the right people and organisations. The campaigns and preliminary activities identified are presented in the sections below. Further activities will be planned and implemented as opportunities are identified and as results emerge. Communication will be planned implemented in careful consideration of Intellectual Property Rights and Innovation Management processes as will be defined in the Data Management Plan and the Dissemination and Exploitation Plan.

Figure 2 Communication campaigns- timeline

6.1 Campaigns for engagement and participation

6.1.1 INFORMATION: Ensure widespread communication around the project and its activity for all audiences

Informative campaign (M1 to M48) it will provide general information about the project, its objectives, update on progress and achievements, provide key facts and figures (e.g., infographics) and promote the outreach activities to ensure wide-scale involvement.

The campaign will span the full duration of the project and focus on static information about the project. The main channel will therefore be the project website with downloadable material (factsheets and infographics) and pages being developed. These will include:

- Lay terms explanations of the project topics and activities

- Short profiles of the partners involved, the external collaborations established and international dimension of the project
- Information on the synergies developed with other projects
- Blog posts from partners, especially the early career researchers.
- The project in numbers and key facts

To create a direct dialogue between the public and the members of the project, researchers in the consortium will be invited to register to “Skype a scientist” an initiative that allows scientists to connect with students around the world and have a video chat with a classroom in a Q&A style.

Finally, as part of the information campaign, a large amount of effort will be deployed for communicating on the flagship missions of the project. These are unique opportunities to produce content and relay messages that are relatable by a large array of stakeholders of all ages and backgrounds. The ability to share content and material produced while exploring the Ocean is a powerful mean to inspire and engage with all. The campaign will include:

Media onboard: Inviting journalists onboard for a scientific mission with Tara and ECO will be part of the strategy to develop media partnerships. Journalists will produce communication material that will be used on all project channels.

Exchanges with crew members: Aimed at students of all ages, the operation offers classes the chance to have regular exchanges with crew members during the missions. With answers to their questions in writing or audio/video, young people’s curiosity about everyday life on board, science, or the environment will be satisfied. Live video- conference meetings between classes and crew members are also planned

Echoes from ports of call - virtual expeditions: stopovers are opportunities to discuss issues of sustainable development around the world. The operation offers young people (8 to 15 years old) the chance to go on a ‘virtual expedition’ to discover the local issues in the country where the schooner is docked which echo more global issues.

Artists in residence: As a part of the efforts to reach general public, TARA and ECO will invite artists for residencies on board. Science has always been a source of inspiration for artists. Aboard the sailing boats, they observe and interpret, according to their sensitivity and imagination, the richness of the Atlantic, the research and daily life in a boat.

6.1.2 AWARENESS: Increase Ocean literacy for all to encourage responsible behaviour towards the ocean

Educative campaign-ocean literacy and public engagement (M1-M48): The campaign will promote upcoming events and programme to local population, Invitation to participate (e.g. school projects) and information on ocean health. This will be achieved via AtlantECO events and training programme with schools, links with multipliers networks, PopSci and news articles, books, social media posts, open science forum appearances (e.g. ESOF), project videos, etc.

Coordinated by UNESCO/IOC, the education actions in AtlantECO will be based on the Ocean Literacy guidelines and principles and linked with the action plan defined for the UN Decade for Ocean sciences and Sustainable development. The IOC-UNESCO Ocean Literacy Portal will have a dedicated section for the AtlantECO project, where all the resources developed will be shared with educators, students and stakeholders. In addition, a dedicated section in the collaborative workspace of the platform will be established to strengthen the exchange between educators, scientists and students.

AtlantECO will carry out activities with organizations such as the Italian Association of Natural Sciences Teachers (ANISN), the Office of Climate Education (OCE), the International Centre of Theoretical Physics (ICTP), the Agence d'Enseignants Français à l'Étranger (AEFE).

UNESCO's national focal points in Brazil and South Africa will be informed and involved in the outreach actions, as part of the effort to promote the Ocean Literacy portal and the Decade for Ocean Sciences.

Building a network of Blue Schools: The project will target schools and teachers in Europe, Brazil and South Africa, especially in countries where the Ocean Literacy actions already exist.

The Communication and outreach team will focus on national educational institutions, to co-develop capacities and guidelines for ocean literacy material with local teacher's associations, public and private education institutions.

The Atlantic Blue Schools network launched during the December 2020 All-Atlantic Forum, is a joint action led by the Federal University of São Paulo (Brazil), Centro Cultural de la Ciencia (Argentina) and Escola Azul - DGPM (Portugal) regarding the implementation of the Blue School programme in Atlantic countries, reaching South America and Africa. The Atlantic Blue Schools network will be supported by AANChOR, Coordination and Support Action project linked with all BG funded projects, including AtlantECO.

Initial set of actions planned In Brazil:

- Support and develop actions with the schools involved in the Blue Schools network, developing specific contents, adapting and translating to Portuguese materials coming from partners
- Participate in the project "Maré de Ciencia", developed by UNIFESP, providing educational tools on Microbiome and plastic pollution.
- Contribute with a microplastic focus to the [MOOC developed by USP](#) for school teachers on the plastics issues.

Initial set of actions planned in South Africa:

- Support and develop actions with the schools involved in the Blue Schools network, developing specific contents, adapting and translating to English and local languages materials coming from partners
- Develop a partnership with the Two Oceans Aquarium, with active participation of UCT, to contribute to the educative program on ocean issues developed with the participation of the Aquarium

Initial set of actions planned in Europe:

- Participate in the Ocean Literacy actions organised in the EU at a regional level
- Bring an Atlantic focus in the Ocean Literacy planned events in Europe by UNESCO/IOC, with support from AANChOR
- Propose a side event on Atlantic Ocean Literacy in the next United Nations Ocean Conference, in Lisbon in June 2021.

6.1.3 CAPACITY BUILDING: Increase capacity to ensure the required resources and skills are available.

An aim is to expand the availability of resources to support sustainable Blue growth for ecosystem services, knowledge creation and exchange, and All-Atlantic collaborations.

Educative campaign- capacity building (M18-M48): to increase capacity and contribute to all-Atlantic community knowledge, for scientist, early career researchers, students and Blue Growth professionals.

The campaign will highlight the opportunity for acquiring skills, provide guidance and explanation on how to participate, detail the content of the training/educative event and highlight the expected learning outcomes. This will be achieved via the capacity building and training programme.

Prior to each event communication efforts will concentrate on promoting the occasion and encourage participation of the relevant audience. This will be done by providing static content on the website with links to programmes, registration pages and updates. This will then be relayed on the more dynamic channels (social media) and distributed in the consortium for spreading.

During the events, short updates will be posted on social media to highlight the key points and increase visibility of partners and speakers.

After events, material will be made available either publicly or to the specific attendees depending on the confidentiality agreements for the event. **A dedicated thematic section will be created on the EMBRC Marine Training portal** where all training activities and resources will be grouped. By doing this via the portal, training seekers will have access to other relevant resources. The training materials will also remain accessible beyond the duration of the project. Communication means will help to promote visibility of the material on the project website.

The communication material targeting educators and students will be submitted to Scientix, a platform promoting and supporting a Europe-wide collaboration among STEM teachers, education researchers, policymakers and other STEM education professionals). We already contacted educators' associations in Europe (e.g., ICTP - Italy), to establish a link with a network of schools (at all levels) that will be involved in the communication events. Links will be established also with the European Schoolnet Network, including 34 European Ministries of Education and related projects (e.g., "All you need is CODE", "Better internet 4 Kids").

6.1.4 PARTICIPATION: promote participation, foster and maintain exchanges with stakeholders

Participative campaign- Science by citizens (M6-M36)

The campaign will aim at achieving optimal participation from scientists and citizens to the efforts of the project. These revolve around 3 main initiatives which will be promoted as follows

Specific events: Prior to each event, communication will provide information to the stakeholders to explain why they should participate, how they can register and what they will need to do. During the events, participants will be encouraged to share short videos and pictures that will be posted on the project social media channels to increase visibility of the efforts and encourage wider participation in subsequent events. After the event a summary of the achievements will be posted on the news section of the website, likely in the form of infographics to highlight the number of participants, the locations covered, etc. and these will be relayed on the social media channels. These will also be included in the issue of the project Newsletter following the event. This will support the following initiative:

All-Atlantic Ocean Sampling Day. OSD which contribute to the AtlantECO sample collection will take place around the Atlantic twice a year on summer and winter solstices in 2021 and 2022.

Continuous involvement: Communication activities will be achieved via a static page on the website where information for interested stakeholders will be provided on how to get involved. AtlantECO social media accounts will diffuse messages pointing to the website page so as to increase awareness around the opportunity to get involved. This will focus on the following initiatives:

All-Atlantic Sail-4-science. The aim is to achieve implementation of a light version of the project protocols by citizen scientists and add 20 sampling lines to those that already exist.

Frugal science: Plankton Planet. With the Plankton planet project, AtlantECO will develop innovative user-friendly tools to underpin a sustainable wind-powered citizen Oceanography 3.0 providing critical new knowledge on global plankton ecology, morphology and genetics that will be universally accessible for scientists, teachers and policymakers. More specifically, Plankton Planet will create:

- An international fleet of Atlantic planktonauts to act as sentinels and collective awareness of the biological health of our oceans
- A toolkit of simple, scientifically relevant instruments for citizen-science assessment of aquatic biodiversity (marine and freshwater).
- A continuous flow of standardized ocean imaging and genetic data at unprecedented spatial, temporal, and taxonomic scales, essential for fundamental and applied science, policymakers, and education.

Participative campaign- Science to Policy (M1-M40): This campaign aims to facilitate the co-creation of knowledge and foster multiway exchanges with Policy makers, regulation bodies, researchers, end-users and ecosystem services providers. In the project, this will be achieved via the five case studies, consultation with the Advisory board and the 6 thematic workshops.

The communication campaign will ensure that information on the case studies, their relevance for society and for sustainable management of the marine resources is available on the project website. Progress and results will be included in the communication material (Newsletter, infographics, videos) as and when relevant.

Each thematic workshop will be promoted as an opportunity for participating in multiway exchanges and contributing to the development of proposals for future research or policy recommendations. Highlights of the events will be posted on the project media channels during and after the workshops.

6.2 Campaigns for action and legacy

The aim of actionable campaigns is to help ensure uptake of AtlantECO results for use.

6.2.1 Actionable campaign - Policy (M36-M48)

The campaign aims to induce change, ensure sustainable long-term impact, addressing decision and policy makers, governments, at the European, Atlantic basin and global scales, and to highlight the availability of recommendations for change based on evidence.

Activities of the project supporting policy engagement are done through the development of policy briefs and the organisation of policy roadshows to promote these. Communication actions to support these will include messages on the project media on the participation of AtlantECO in political/institutional events and the material that will be presented, including the recommendations developed. These will be made available on the project website and the permanent repository Zenodo. Besides, this communication will be developed further during the project as the plan for use of results is defined in the Dissemination and Exploitation Plan.

6.2.2 Actionable campaign- Blue Economy (M24-M48)

Project activities to support Blue Growth include implementation of application case studies as well as participation in conferences, institutional events and at trade fairs.

The campaign will support these activities by communicating the progress and achievements made, including information on the new products and services that were made possible through AtlantECO activities and results. It will be guided by the strategies defined in the Dissemination and Exploitation Plan.

6.2.3 Actionable campaign- Future activities (M46-M48)

An important legacy of the project will be to compile results, contributions and lessons learnt into a roadmap for future activities during the final stages of the project. The roadmap will be built gradually throughout the project and will be released during the final AtlantECO conference.

During the project, communication activities done in other campaigns will have helped to announce the development of the roadmap and provided information for individuals and organisations interested in contributing to it. This ultimate short campaign will therefore focus on the promotion of the final conference to ensure a large attendance from all sectors. During the event, communication material will be presented to showcase all achievements of the project (infographics and final video, posters from the early career researchers, etc) and these will be available after the project on the project website and permanent repository Zenodo.

Pending approval

7 Communication resources

7.1 Branding

The support all communication activities, AtlantECO has developed its branding early on in the project. This is used on all material and platforms to ensure that the project image is identifiable by all over time.

7.1.1 Logos

The AtlantECO logo has been declined in multiple formats to allow an array of use and media support. Its main elements are the project acronym, the project title, and a set of six critters. The background for each version is either transparent, white, dark blue or dark grey. Below are some examples of the logo in different formats.

7.1.1.1 Full official logo

7.1.1.2 Acronym and critters-long

7.1.1.3 Acronym and critters- square

7.1.1.4 Critters only

7.1.2 Colour palette

The following colours are used in AtlantECO branding

	HEX: #575756	R: 87; G: 87; B: 86
	HEX: #174571	R: 23; G: 69; B: 113
	HEX: #136EB9	R: 19; G: 110; B: 185
	HEX: #3192F0	R: 49; G: 146; B: 240
	HEX: #35A8E0	R: 53; G: 168; B: 224
	HEX: #46BC1E	R: 70; G: 188; B: 30
	HEX: #F5A733	R: 245; G: 167; B: 51
	HEX: #E5007E	R: 229; G: 0; B: 126
	HEX: #BF7590	R: 191; G: 117; B: 114

Figure 3 AtlantECO branding-colour palette

7.1.3 Font

The AtlantECO font is “Overlock Regular 400” available for [download on Google fonts](#).

7.1.4 Formatting and documents

In order to ensure uniform formatting of documents, templates have been prepared for use by all beneficiaries for reports, deliverable reports, agendas and minutes, presentations, and basic text documents. Additional templates will be developed as needed.

7.1.5 External resources to complement the brand

The project has been and will be collaborating with existing and new partners for additional visual content (photography, vectors, videos, etc.) and will be crediting the source of all material when it is used.

This collaboration already includes agreements to use of images from [Planktomania](#) from which vectors were used as inspiration for the project logo, and the use of imagery from [Plankton Chronicles](#) on the project website.

7.2 Developing communication content

7.2.1 Roles and responsibilities

Development of content is a collective responsibility of the project partners. All beneficiaries will be asked to provide content that will form the basis of communication material.

Design and alignment of material produced with project branding will be done by FTO.

Development and maintenance of the project stakeholder database, in line with GDPR requirements, is SPI.

7.2.2 Approval process

Process of evaluation of innovation potential: prior to communication of project results, all material will follow the assessment for innovation potential as will be described in the Dissemination and Exploitation Plan. This will prevent issues where Intellectual Property with potential for protection and/or commercial exploitation is made public before the appropriate protection measures are implemented.

Review and approval process:

- For day-to-day communication material no process of approval will be necessary. This covers dynamic material produced for social media and information that is already publicly available.
- For material supporting specific events or communication aims, including press kits et major press releases, the partners directly involved in the relevant activities will be asked for review and approval before publication.
- Further procedures on how to handle project foreground with possible innovation potential will be detailed in the Dissemination and Exploitation Plan, primarily being based on the responsibility of the project partner(s) producing such foreground in the light of the innovation goals of the Horizon 2020 framework programme and assisted by project internal and external resources.

7.3 Delivering communication: resources, material and events.

To implement the communication plan, a set of communication material and resources will be developed, and events will be organised. These will be deployed in the communication campaigns as highlighted in the previous sections. These are presented in the following sections.

7.3.1 Communication kit

AtlantECO communication and outreach tools will be designed to be accessible and engaging and will consider cultural and gender diversity to ensure that the solutions are appealing to all audiences. All resources will be developed using non-technical language in English. Some of the material will be translated in Portuguese, French, Italian, Afrikaans and any other language as required to engage with global audiences. Audio-visual material will contain subtitles.

AtlantECO visual content:

Photos, infographics, videos and animations will present the general concept of the proposal and milestones, its impact and the involvement of stakeholders.

Figure 4 The AtlantECO logo, displayed on Tara, flagship vessel for the sampling Mission Microbiomes. (Source: FTO)

Press kits will be developed throughout the project to support the communication campaigns and activities.

Press kits will be developed around major events and include interviews of AtlantECO members, infographics, information material on the project, access to visual content to be used by journalists and media outlets for press articles and posts (photos, videos, logos). Figure 5 illustrates an example of infographics from the press kit produced for the departure of Tara for Mission Microbiomes, one of the flagship sampling missions of the project:

Figure 5 Example of infographics produced for press kits

All material will be available in digital (downloadable) format so as to avoid printed material which will only be used when digital media are not relevant or possible.

Newsletter

The public newsletter for the project will be produced on a quarterly basis and sent out to the subscribers who are registering through the website.

The newsletter will provide a summary of the progress and achievements of the project, present the project partners and their collaborators and provide information on upcoming events, or opportunities to get involved, so as to support the more specific communication campaigns defined above. The newsletter will utilise material such as images and infographics which will also be relayed on social media

Kids magazine

A special edition of FTO's magazine "Tara Ocean, Le Mag" will be developed. The magazine will contain about 8 pages and target 8-15 years old children. It will contain infographics, pictures and accessible text to explain the scientific foci of the project. The digital version will be promoted on the project website, and through the UNESCO-IOC Ocean Literacy Portal and shared with a large audience and target specifically teachers and young people.

Art & Science

As part of the flagship Mission Microbiomes, artists in residence will be hosted on board the Tara schooner and produce artistic material (illustrations, sculptures, photography, videos) inspired by the mission and the scientific concepts underpinning it. The material will help to broaden ways of communicating on the Ocean and reach audiences beyond those traditionally targeted in scientific research.

7.3.2 Communication channels

7.3.2.1 Project channels

AtlantECO website (www.atlanteco.eu) is the main communication channel and the point of access to resources generated and related to AtlantECO.

Figure 6 Screen shot of the AtlantECO website home page.

The AtlantECO website has been launched (Figure 6) and contains the pages which have been developed to date. Further developments are planned to achieve the structure illustrated in Figure 7.

Figure 7 AtlantECO website structure

The website will be continuously updated and developed as the project progresses and to address additional needs when they are identified.

AtlantECO social media

AtlantECO has accounts on Twitter, Facebook and Instagram to share scientific progresses and updates, to follow the flagship vessels and build an open image gallery, a YouTube channel has been set up to disseminate

project related videos (Figure 8).

Social media channels will be primarily used for news, outreach, business and political content (Twitter) as well as visual and educative, awareness raising content with interactions e.g. quizzes and surveys (Instagram and Facebook).

Figure 8 AtlantECO social media accounts (Facebook not pictured)

7.3.2.2 Multipliers networks

Links established with other initiatives, projects and networks will be used to ensure that there is a multilateral sharing of information and resources where it is applicable and relevant. In addition, this will help prevent stakeholder fatigue by combining existing resources, material and networks around similar communication goals across multiple projects. For example, all-Atlantic networks will be reached through AANCHOR, whereas audience specific material will be relayed by selected members of the synergy groups. Specifically, AtlantECO will also engage with the youth platforms to support the communication activities with young people.

Coordination with other projects and All-Atlantic sister projects through AANCHOR.

Beyond the specific issues and key messages in AtlantECO, the project will promote an "Atlantic" narrative, linked with the All-Atlantic sister projects and coordinated with the support and coordination action AANCHOR. Among all the All-Atlantic projects, AtlantECO is the only project focusing on Microbiome and Plasticsphere at this level, and we will search to contribute to joint activities and common communication tools with sister projects.

AtlantECO WP leaders are already participating in the joint working groups promoted by AANCHOR and will contribute to many joint activities. Furthermore, where appropriate AtlantECO will develop synergies on communication with other projects and initiatives where complementary activities will help deliver more impactful messages to common stakeholders.

Support and coordination with the youth platforms

AtlantECO will engage and collaborate with the existing initiatives which are led by young people who are involved in Ocean related activities. These include the Youth4Ocean Forum, the All-Atlantic Ocean Youth Ambassadors, and the Orienting Young Scientists of EuromaRine (OYSTER) group. Communication messages will be co-developed around the subject matter of AtlantECO project and the youth perspective.

7.3.3 AtlantECO communication events

7.3.3.1 AtlantECO press engagement

Throughout the AtlantECO project, we will have an efficient media engagement strategy focusing on AtlantECO milestones and results working with international and local media. Depending on the messages over what has been accomplished and the areas of action we will work with mainstream media, scientific press, and/or political press.

We will be sending press release, press kits, organising digital or face to face press conferences or media exclusivity depending on the extent of press coverage desired in line with the nature of the communication needs. This will be done following the pyramid of goals:

- **Make AtlantECO known:** what is AtlantECO, its goals, why it exists, which stakeholders need to know, what is its uniqueness
- **Promote understanding:** actions, differentiating elements, stories, results
- **Generate support:** to use the results and promote usefulness to the common good

7.3.3.2 AtlantECO Port calls:

AtlantECO will bridge the ocean sciences to the general public, through general communication and outreach activities, but also with concrete actions with the scientific vessels, especially with the sailing boats Tara and Veleiro Eco. All AtlantECO flagships will contribute to outreach activities, particularly at stopovers on board research sailing vessels Tara and Veleiro ECO and where possible other vessels such as Eugen Seibold, where ocean literacy activities will be organised with the public and scientific training on Imaging & genetic protocols will be organised with Ocean Sampling Day participants. At each stopover, the crew will invite students and their teachers onboard to share AtlantECO's discoveries and adventures. All categories of stakeholders will be invited onboard and be offered guided tours by scientists, sailors and Ocean governance experts. Visitors will learn about life on board, daily work of scientists, history of the ships, navigation, and the ecological problems of the oceans. The dynamics created during these visits to a "floating scientific lab" is powerful and will help to bring youngsters and ocean lovers towards an "Atlantic Ocean" community.

7.3.3.3 Events to be attended by AtlantECO

The Ocean governance agenda has entered an important period, with several International conferences and political processes to support decisions on ocean policies, the launch of the Ocean Decade, the High Seas biodiversity treaty, the Paris agreement, the sustainable development Goals (e.g., SDG14) and others. AtlantECO will be promoting the All-Atlantic Vision with contents about our specific niches – Microbiome, Plastisphere, Seascape – in these different fora. Scientific conferences and side events will be proposed during identified conferences. Initial opportunities have been identified to contribute to the UN Ocean Conference (UNOC) in Lisbon (2021), the Azores EU Atlantic Meeting (2021); occurrences of the All-Atlantic Forums, the UNFCCC COP26 side event, and Decade for Ocean Sciences events. Further opportunities will be identified throughout the project duration.

7.3.3.4 AtlantECO exhibitions

During the project, an exhibition will be developed on the Ocean Microbiome, Plastics & the plastisphere and Seascape & Connectivity. The portable multimedia exhibitions consisting of panels for outdoor exhibit set up during the port of call will be made available for all vessels and all events in the project. Digital versions will also be made available for download from the Media channels.

An ambition will be to scope opportunities to offer an updated version of the exhibit to museums or other institutions in Brazil, South Africa and Europe. The realisation of this endeavour will depend on the possibility to secure co-funding. Preliminary discussions have been initiated and yielded positive responses with Museu do Amanha (Rio de Janeiro, BR), the Two Oceans Aquarium (Cape Town, SA) and Universcience, (Paris, France).

7.3.3.5 *AtlantECO final conference*

At the end of the project, the final conference will be organised. The event will launch the Roadmap for future activities which will present recommendations for future activities (scientific, research, policy, capacity building, awareness raising, technology development, etc.) based on the results, lessons learnt and achievements of the AtlantECO project. This will be a major event for the project and communication activities will help promote the event so that attendance from all targeted sectors is achieved. A comprehensive press kit will be prepared to highlight all project activities, and digital content created during the project will be showcased at the event, (e.g., films, photography, exhibition material).

Pending approval

8 Monitoring and measuring impact

8.1 Monitoring and reporting communication activities in the project

In order to record the activities and capture all material produced, a Google form has been developed. It follows the structure for continuous reporting so as to streamline processes from activity to recording. This will enable FTO to follow up with partners to measure the impact of each communication activity and report on metrics in line with the Key Performance Indicators presented below in the Periodic and Final Reports.

8.2 Key Performance Indicators

Activity	Key Performance Indicators
Continuous publicity	Metrics: Number of TV & press releases, and public newsletters Target: 2 major press events/publications and at least 4 newsletters per year.
Website	Metrics: Website hits, page views, deliverable/document downloads, comments received, requests for information received, subscriptions to the newsletter. Target: At least 10,000 visits in 4 years.
Social Media	Metrics: Engagement rates (including page likes and followers, post clicks, likes, comments and shares) Target: A total of 4000+ followers across social media platforms after 4 years.
Videos	Metrics: number of videos produced, and number of views and engagement (likes, shares, comments). Target: At least 4 videos on the project uploaded on the YouTube channel, shorter audio-visual content created for social media platforms (e.g., Instagram stories, Twitter Fleets).
Open Access Publications	Metrics: Number of publications of scientific results in peer reviewed journals and popular science media. Target: >20 scientific papers from the second year and 1 non-technical publication per year.
Policy	Metrics: number of policy related events organised/attended; number of recommendations developed. Target: 3 policy roadshows and 3 policy briefs/recommendations.
Citizen science	Metrics: number of citizen science initiatives, number of participants Target Sail-4-science 20 sampling lines.
Capacity building	Delivery of 6 thematic workshops including participants from North and South Atlantic countries from all sectors. 4 Summer schools: 2 internal and 2 synergy. At least 10 one day training for OSD activities.
Port call	Metrics: number of port calls and associated events, number of visitors Target: 25 port calls with open ship, ocean literacy and outreach events.
Webinars and Conferences	Metrics: number of events organised, number of attendees. Target: 12 ESR organised webinars, 1 final conference.